



This vector allows expression in *E. coli* of the MRP1 full length protein (13283 in the map), tagged with 6xHIS-HALO7 (PMID:23248739) at the N-terminal end, cleavable from the protein of interest with 3C protease. All protocols regarding this expression system are available at: <https://www.oppf.rc-harwell.ac.uk/OPPF/protocols/>